
ECONOMIC ADVANTAGES OF WASTE HEAT RECOVERY BOILERS OVER COMBUSTION BOILERS IN PLANTS WITH HIGH EXHAUST HEAT

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ABSTRACT

In a sponge iron plant, the exit gases from rotary kiln (pyro processing device) has a peak average temperature of 850°C to 950°C. Although it is possible to convert these waste heat into usable power, such potentials are not fully realized because most of the industries, particularly in Asia, continue to operate with older systems. The appreciable volumes of heat released are cooled by cooling systems before the flue gases are released into the environment. These cooling systems requires power to operate in addition to the power requirements of the plant, which are produced by combustion boilers. However, waste heat recovery boilers (WHRB) converts such heat into functional energy by eliminating the cooling systems. In addition to that, the installation and operation costs of WHRB are lower than combustion boilers. WHRB not only produces operable power but also reduces the emission of pollutants since waste heat acts as the fuel source instead of external fuel source. Therefore, the importance of such conversion techniques are emphasized in terms of economic analysis to reduce the use of conventional energy sources and use the available resources to its maximum potential.

Keywords: Waste heat recovery boiler; steam generation; fluidized bed combustion; economic analysis; energy.

1. INTRODUCTION

Conventional fuels are exhausted every day, which are under regulations for its use due to environmental impacts. Although energy from solar, tidal and wind are increasingly adopted worldwide, the capital and time needed to generate enough quantity to operate an industry, iron processing in particular, is difficult to meet with alternative fuels. In such cases, conventional fuels source i.e., coals are widely used to meet these requirements.

India, being an energy dependent country because of diverse climatic conditions, uses conventional fuel sources for most of the energy demands. Be it for domestic, commercial or industrial usage, the requirements are most commonly met with use of coals and the coals used in India are Grade 7 i.e., bituminous coal, a widely available resource. India is among the top five countries for global carbon dioxide emissions in recent years. The total CO₂ emission per capita is still greater than 1.5 tonnes (Olivier et al. 2015). This is considered high because India is among the top three countries for both energy consumption as well as production of coal. The present energy produced by burning coals are 1130 terawatt hour (TWh) but these are not enough to meet the energy demands, which is expected to reach 4000 TWh by 2040 (Penney et al. 2015). Arguments does rise about the use of bio-waste as burning fuel but from an engineering point of view, the consideration of calorific values supersedes these arguments. Hence, bio-wastes can be used only as a combination along with coal as fuel.

From various advancements in iron processing industries, the most interesting development is the use of waste heat recovery system (WHRS) as a tool to replace cooling systems in fluidised bed combustion system (FBCS), especially atmospheric fluidised bed combustion system (AFBCS) in a sponge iron plant (recovery systems are typically used as an additional arrangement). In FBCS, the rotary kiln of a sponge iron plant emits large quantities of heat. These heat are in turn cooled by gas coolers before they are released as flue gases into the environment (Koorneef et al. 2007). Power is required to operate these cooling systems, which is produced by atmospheric fluidised bed combustion boilers (AFBCB) (Hughes et al. 2005) or circulating fluidized bed combustion boilers (CFBCB). Both rotary kiln as well as combustion boilers requires fuel (coal) to operate (Fig. 1). In case of WHRS, WHRB replaces AFBCB and its improved version i.e., CFBCB (most efficient in its family; the major difference is that CFBCB can use wide variety of fuel combinations) (Nag et al. 1987). The heat from rotary kiln is converted into power and hence, only the rotary kiln requires fuel to operate since the cooling systems are eliminated (Fig. 2). Based on this design, this work highlights resource utilizations, environmental impacts and economic advantages in the field and emphasizes the importance of implementing such techniques for energy conservation in industrial sectors.

Fig-1: Layout in a sponge iron plant with AFBCB or CFBCB

Fig-2: Waste heat recovery steam generation (WHRSG) in sponge iron industry

2. METHOD

In AFBCB system (Fig. 1) the energy produced from the boilers are used to operate the gas cooler. The average energy requirement for its operation is 35 MW/hr (megawatt / hour). Similarly, the average energy requirement for electrostatic precipitators (ESP) and induced draft (ID) fan are 93 kW/hr and 55 kW/hr respectively (Chandramohan, 2013). The remaining energy produced is utilized by the plant for general requirements such as lights, fans and etc., where the power is produced by burning coals. In WHRSG system (Fig. 2) however, the exit heat from rotary kiln were used as fuel, which averaged at 900°C. This heat is ultimately used to produce superheated steam for power generation similar to combustion boilers. The generated power is then used to satisfy the electrical requirements of ESP, ID fan and rest of the plant (Loganathan et al. 2013). The fuel used for AFBCB was ‘55% coal + 25% char + 20% rice husk’ with a combined gross calorific value of 2300 kcal/kg. Although, variants such as ‘coal fines, dolochar and pet coke’ in combinations with coal can also be used as fuels for CFBCB.

3. COMPARISON BETWEEN AFBCD AND WHRB

For comparisons, AFBCB of 30 TPH (tonnes per hour) capacity with an efficiency of $84 \pm 2\%$ and WHRB of 11 TPH capacity with an efficiency of $80 \pm 2\%$ are considered. 1 TPH generates approximately 2.2 MW (megawatt) power, which signifies the power generation capacity of the boiler; higher the capacity, more the need for fuel. These two different capacities are compared because on a lower scale, the performance as well as construction costs are relatively equivalent. Both boilers were designed at 67 ATA (atmospheric pressure absolute) at an outlet super heater temperature of $490 \pm 5^\circ\text{C}$. Due to high exit heat from rotary kiln, WHRB was designed based on the gas flow rate of $25 \text{ kNm}^3/\text{hr}$ at 975°C at the inlet. In contrast, AFBCB was designed at a net heat input capacity of 25.4 megacalorie / hour (MCal/hr). In both of these systems, the average gas density of flue gases were 1.3 kg/Nm^3 and the CO_2 content were lesser for WHRB at 13.35% than 17% with AFBCB (Chandramohan, 2013). The final flue gas temperature in WHRB system was at 170°C (inlet capacity of 975°C). This signifies that an average of 82% of the total heat from rotary kiln were utilized in WHRS compared to 50% by AFBCS (Chandramohan 2013, Loganathan 2013). The major difference being the 30% to 40% extra heat (as illustrated in Fig. 3) that was converted into usable power for electrical requirements of the plant.

Fig-3: Break-up of total heat produced

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The economic analysis were made by comparing WHRB with AFBCB in terms of equipment (construction), fuel and power production.

4.1. Equipment cost

As mentioned earlier, rotary kiln requires fuel to operate and hence, most equipment such as fans, valves, feeders, pumps, dosing systems, fuel and ash handling systems and etc. are in common with AFBCS. Hence, the equipment mentioned in Tab. 1. alone differs (Chandramohan, 2013).

Tab-1: Equipment cost differences

Equipment	WHRB	AFBCB
Electric overhead traveling (EOT) crane	x	✓
Soot blowers	✓	x
Cooling tower	x	✓

The only equipment cost for WHRB (as illustrated in Fig. 4, with \$ 1 = ₹ 63.5 - median average during the work) was soot blowers that was at \$ 7,874 based on the market price in India (Chandramohan, 2013). In case of AFBCB, EOT crane costs at \$ 7,086 and cooling tower at \$ 787,401. Therefore, the equipment cost for AFBCB was more than 100 times when compared with WHRB.

Fig-4: Equipment costs by construction

4.2. Fuel cost

The AFBCB requires external fuel source to operate, where 30 TPH capacity of AFBCB requires burning of 2 TPH of coals. With the average cost of coal in India at \$ 78.7 per ton (during the work) and the operating time per day at 8 hours (Chandramohan, 2013):

Fuel cost per day:

= Fuel consumed at TPH * cost of coal per ton in \$ * operating time in hours

= 2 * 78.7 * 8

= \$ 1,259

Considering five working days per week, the fuel cost (as illustrated in Fig. 5) becomes \$ 25,196 per month and \$ 302,362 per year for AFBCB. WHRB does not require any external fuel source since it uses exit heat from rotary kiln as input and hence, fuel cost per month and annum for WHRB is \$ 0.

Fig-5: Fuel costs for the use of coal

4.3. Power production cost

Power production cost involves the consideration of all available resources, including workforce. By Indian industrial standards (during the work), typical production cost for a kWhr (kilowatt-hour) for WHRB and AFBCB were \$ 0.02 and \$ 0.07 respectively (Chandramohan, 2013).

Power generated per day = (Power generated by boiler in kW * operating time in hours)

For WHRB:

= (11 * 2.2 * 1000) * 8

= 193,600 kWhr

For AFBCB:

= (30 * 2.2 * 1000) * 8

= 528,000 kWhr

Production cost per day = (Production cost in \$ per kWhr * power generated per day)

For WHRB:

= 0.02 * 193,600

= \$ 3,872

For AFBCB:

= 0.07 * 528,000

= \$ 36,960

Considering five working days per week, the production cost (as illustrated in Fig .6) per month becomes \$ 77,440 for WHRB and \$ 443,520 for AFBCB. Similarly, it costs \$ 929,280 per year for WHRB and \$ 5,322,240 per year for AFBCB. Therefore, production cost per annum for AFBCB was more than 5 times when compared with WHRB.

Fig-6: Production costs for power at the plant

4.4. Profits

After satisfying the electrical requirements of the plant, the ratio of surplus power to total power produced per day (8 hours consideration) were 40 kW : 193.6 MW for WHRB and 145 kW : 528 MW for AFBCB. The surplus power were exported to grid by wheeling and the peak average cost earned was \$ 0.09 / KW (during the work) (Chandramohan, 2013).

$$\text{Earning per day} = \text{Selling cost in \$ per kW} * \text{surplus power in kW}$$

For WHRB:

$$= 0.09 * 40$$

$$= \$ 3.6$$

For AFBCB:

$$= 0.09 * 145$$

$$= \$ 13$$

Considering five working days per week, the profits per month (as illustrated in Fig. 7) becomes \$ 72 for WHRB and \$ 261 for AFBCB. Similarly, profits per year becomes \$ 864 for WHRB and \$ 3,132. Although the profits per annum through export is more for AFBCB, the cost spent on fuel per year alone is \$ 302,362, whereas it is \$ 0 for WHRB Therefore, the use of WHRB effectively makes the plant ‘independent’. However, it can also be classified as a ‘captive’ if the surplus power were to be stored for personal use instead of exporting.

Fig.-7: Profits by exporting the surplus power

4.5. Market

The reason for unfavourable WHRS installation is regular maintenance. As with any boilers, maintenance is necessary to prolong its life. However, WHRB requires additional care in order to maintain its efficiency. It is to be noted that 11 TPH capacity of WHRB has an efficiency of 80 % when compared to 30 TPH capacity of AFBCB with efficiency of 84 %. For the same application, the WHRB operates only at 36 % capacity of the AFBCB with significantly lesser costs. Even without the consideration of equipment or production costs, WHRBs are economically viable in terms of fuel cost alone. Therefore, it is up to the users to realize such potentials and also with the manufacturers to advice well.

5. MERITS OF WHRSG

- Effective utilization of energy resources in the plant i.e., 80% to 90% of the total heat.
- Eliminates external fuel source for boilers, thereby reducing the pollutants.
- Eliminates gas cooler and its power requirement, thereby saving power.
- Significantly reduces the costs in 'equipment, fuel and production'.

6. CONCLUSION

In any combustion process, heat is generated by burning fuels. Most of the time however, these heats are wasted without realizing its potential that ultimately brings an energy dependency. Therefore, it is important to advocate methods to reduce such dependency and to make use of available resources more efficiently when and where applicable. Through sponge iron industry, a case was made in terms of economic analysis, where attaining self-sufficiency in power usage was one of the primary goals for long-term gain as well as being relatively eco-friendly to the environment. Therefore, systems with 'ovens, incinerators, engine exhausts, crackers, dryers, castings, furnaces, and etc.', which are much similar to rotary kiln may also be promoted to realize such potentials.

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